

DETERMINATION OF PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL INDICATORS OF WATER FROM DIFFERENT SOURCES**Zadorozhna O.,***Pavlo Tychyna Uman State Pedagogical University;
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Pavlo Tychyna Uman State Pedagogical University, Uman, Ukraine***ABSTRACT**

Quality water is a liquid whose physical and chemical characteristics meet the standards of the International Health Organization (WHO). Only if the characteristics of drinking water match these standards, it can be considered suitable for use.

The purpose of the work. Study of the quality of drinking water from different sources of its supply in the Cherkasy region.

Keywords: chemical composition, drinking water, chlorides, sulfates, hydrogen index.

Formulation of the problem. Providing the population with good quality drinking water is the main task of society today. The use of low-quality water for one's vital needs threatens the health of the nation. One of the reasons for the unsatisfactory quality of drinking water in Ukraine is the pollution of surface water bodies by discharges into them of large quantities of untreated and insufficiently treated household, industrial and agricultural wastewater, melt water from fields, the territories of villages and cities. Violation of the underground water regime as a result of long-term operation of artesian wells, groundwater pollution, deterioration of the sanitary and technical condition of distribution water networks also contributes to the pollution of drinking water.

The most common problem with water quality is its high hardness, which is caused by the total amount of dissolved alkaline earth metal ions, calcium Ca^{2+} and magnesium Mg^{2+} are usually taken into account, since they make up at least 98-99% of all compounds. To a lesser extent, beryllium, strontium and barium affect the hardness - these metals belong to the group of heavy, so they are regulated separately by stricter standards. Water full of calcium and magnesium ions worsens organoleptic indicators, it negatively affects the skin and digestive organs, and the cardiovascular system suffers excessively. Long-term use of hard water can lead to joint diseases (arthritis, polyarthritis), the formation of stones in the kidneys and bile ducts.

Methods of research. Volumetric (titration), photometric (colorimetric), analytical and diagnostic; comprehensive, retrospective and comparative analyzes (to identify cause-and-effect relationships regarding the anthropogenic transformation of hydroecosystems)

Analysis of recent research and publications.

A person drinks about 750 liters of water per year, of which 70% is water. Exchange of substances, maintenance of heat balance, removal of toxins and decay products - all this is carried out by water. Therefore,

the water must be of satisfactory quality, since the presence of impurities in the water can cause significant damage to the human body and initiate the development of many diseases. Providing the population with high-quality and safe drinking water for human health is guaranteed by the legislation of Ukraine [1-4]. According to the World Health Organization, 80% of human diseases are associated with water quality and are the cause of death of 2.2 million people every year [5].

A number of scientists are currently studying the quality of drinking water. The assessment carried out according to integral indicators shows that only three out of ten sources have water of good quality according to indicators, which, with certain assumptions, can be considered suitable for drinking purposes.

Drinking water with physico-chemical parameters that deviate from acceptable norms has a negative effect on the human body and can cause a number of diseases. The hydrogen indicator indicates the acid-alkaline balance of water. The corrosive aggressiveness of the liquid, the speed of chemical reactions and the degree of toxicity of pollutants directly depend on it. Scientists believe that the pH of water should approximately correspond to the norm of pH of human blood, which is equal to 7.5

Chlorides have high solubility and therefore are present in all natural waters mainly in the form of calcium, sodium and magnesium salts. Their entry into the water is facilitated by the leaching of table salt and other chlorine compounds from the layers of rocks of volcanic origin. A huge amount of chlorides is contained in the seas and oceans. Through the atmospheric cycle, water, precipitation, and with underground currents of salt enter all other bodies of water. However, many chlorides enter water with industrial and domestic runoff [6-9].

Water oversaturated with chlorides can cause damage to mucous membranes, eyes, skin and respiratory tract. After drinking such water, the water-salt balance and the work of the digestive tract are disturbed.

An excess of salts leads to changes in blood vessels, overloading of the heart and kidneys, an increase in blood pressure and can significantly aggravate the course of cardiovascular diseases [10].

Nitrates and nitrites are salts of nitric acid that are widely used as cheap and effective fertilizers. Directly from agricultural fields, they penetrate into the soil and open water bodies. The same industrial and livestock wastes, the use of household chemicals and septic tanks near wells and wells contribute to the spread of this group of substances.

More often, excess concentration of nitrates in water is observed in surface waters, less often in deep sources. It is very important to control the content of nitrates in water in areas with agricultural fields.

In such areas, nitrates can be contained in the water of wells and springs in large quantities [11]. Water poisoning, which contains a lot of nitrites, causes damage to the gastrointestinal tract.

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Results.

Five water samples were selected for analysis in the Cherkasy region:

- 1 - water from a centralized water supply
- 2 – water from a spring (the village of Subotiv);
- 3 – water from a well (Legedzyno village);
- 4 – water from a well (Uman city);
- 5 - water from filling points.

Table 1.

Indicators of the chemical composition of water, mg/dm ³						
№	Indexes	Sample				
		1	2	3	4	5
1.	Chlorides	30,4	44	40	35,1	39,5
2.	Nitrates	2,9	4,3	7,8	12,6	3,1
3.	Nitrite	0,005	0,009	0,036	0,032	0,019
4.	Ammonium	0,25	0,11	0,33	0,41	0,17
5.	Common iron	0,20	0,31	0,18	0,11	0,25

Chloride content in drinking water should not exceed 250 mg/dm³ for tap water and 350 mg/dm³ for water from wells and springs. The characteristics of the chloride content did not show exceeding the maximum allowable concentrations. Analysis of the chloride content showed that the content in the samples is insignificant, far from the MPC values, and ranges from 30.4 to 44 mg/dm³

The rest of the indicators were also within the permissible limits, but they differed significantly from each other.

Fig. 1. Hydrogen index, pH

As can be seen from the data in Figure 2, the pH of the studied water samples is in the norm, which is set at the level of 6.5 - 8.5

Fig. 2. Total hardness mmol/dm³

The most favorable for a person is the consumption of water with a total hardness of 3–4 mmol/dm³, in tap water the indicator should not be more than 7 mmol/dm³. The analysis showed that the water in all the selected samples is within the normal range.

Fig. 3. Organoleptic assessment of water, score

The main organoleptic indicators of water are color, color, turbidity, transparency, smell, taste and aftertaste.

The color of natural waters can be of different shades. In many cases, the color of the water is due to the presence of microorganisms, products of their vital activity and decay, as well as silt particles, sulfides, and other substances suspended in the water [12].

Chromaticity is a quantitative characteristic of color, which is expressed in conventional units - degrees of chroma. It is determined according to the bichromate-cobalt scale or using the KFK-2 device (photoelectric concentration colorimeter).

The turbidity of water depends on finely dispersed impurities in the form of suspended particles (sand, clay, silt, algae), which enter it as a result of coastal erosion, with rainwater and meltwater. Qualitative determination is carried out descriptively. For example, water can be transparent, opalescent, cloudy, etc. The quantitative value of turbidity is expressed in mg/l and is determined using the KFK-2 device.

The transparency of water depends on its color and turbidity. The measure of transparency is the height of the water column, in cm, through which a standard font can be read [13].

The smell of water is caused by volatile odorous substances, dissolved salts, organic compounds and products of their vital activities, which enter the water naturally and with sewage. In natural waters containing only inorganic substances, only hydrogen sulfide, which is present in some polluted groundwater, can give the smell. The smell of drinking water obtained by treating surface water is due to the properties of the raw water used, the technological process of improving its quality, and the method of treatment. For example, after chlorination, water containing phenols acquires an unpleasant smell of chlorophenols. The smell of groundwater and surface water is affected by the presence of organic substances. Wastewater pollution is manifested not only by the appearance of an odor, but also by the smell of the decomposition products of their components. When determining the smell of drinking, surface or sewage water, in all cases, the nature of the smell (chlorine, fishy, etc.) is first established. Next, its intensity is determined, which is done either organoleptically, expressing the intensity of the smell on a five-point scale, or by conducting a "threshold" study - diluting the analyzed water until the smell disappears [14].

Taste and aftertaste. The taste qualities of water are determined by the presence of substances of natural origin or substances that enter the water as a result of pollution by its effluents. Groundwater containing only inorganic dissolved substances has a specific taste, which is caused by the presence of iron, manganese, sodium, potassium, chlorides, etc. elements. We define the taste of drinking water only, describe it verbally. There are four main types of taste: salty, sour, bitter, sweet. All other types of taste sensations are called sweets [15].

Conclusions. It was investigated that water samples in the Cherkasy region taken from various sources fully meet the requirements for the quality of drinking water. Chlorides, nitrates, nitrites, ammonium, total iron content, water content and total hardness are within the limits of maximum permissible norms. Organoleptic indicators of water are satisfactory.

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